

Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean

M3.4 Application of the Surrogate Models Under Different Scenarios (Climate and Socio-Economic Changes, Remediation Strategies)

VERSION 1

Acknowledgment: This project is part of the PRIMA Programme supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No 1923.

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7896090

Project Information

Project Title	Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean		
Project Acronym	InTheMED	Grant Agreement Number	1923
Program	Horizon 2020		
Type of Action	Water RIA – Research and Innovation Action		
Start Data	March 1, 2020	Duration	36 months
Project Coordinator	Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), Spain		
Consortium	<p>Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV), Spain</p> <p>Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung (UFZ), Germany</p> <p>Università degli Studi di Parma (UNIPR), Italy</p> <p>Boğaziçi Üniversitesi (BU), Turkey</p> <p>Centre de Recherches et des Technologies des Eaux (CERTE), Tunisie</p> <p>Technical University of Crete (TUC), Greece</p> <p>Associação do Instituto Superior Técnico para a Investigação e Desenvolvimento (IST-ID), Portugal</p>		

Document Information

Deliverable Number	M3.4	Deliverable Name	Application of the Surrogate Models Under Different Scenarios (Climate and Socio-Economic Changes, Remediation Strategies)	
Work Package number	WP3	Work Package Title	Innovative Smart Modelling in the MED	
Due Date	Contractual (revised)	April 30, 2023	Actual	4 May, 2023
Version Number	1.0			
Deliverable Type	Report (R)	Dissemination Level	Public (PU)	
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Reviewer(s)	All			

Document History

Version	Date	Stage	Reviewed by
0.1	29/03/2023	Contribution from UPV partner team have been added	All
0.2	12/04/2023	Review of the document	All
1.0	03/05/2023	First version	All

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Executive Summary

The overall objective of the InTheMED project is to implement innovative and sustainable management tools and remediation strategies for MED aquifers (inland and coastal) in order to mitigate anthropogenic and climate-change threats by creating new long-lasting spaces of social learning among different interdependent stakeholders, NGOs, and scientific researchers in five field case studies. These are located at the two shores of the MED basin, namely in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia, and Turkey.

InTheMED will develop an inclusive process that will establish an ensemble of innovative assessment and management tools and methodologies including a high-resolution monitoring approach, smart modelling, a socio-economic assessment, web-based decision support systems (DSS) and new configurations for governance to validate efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED considering both the quantitative and qualitative aspects.

This Milestone, namely M3.4, is part of Task 3.4 “Analysis of Different Scenarios” (Lead: UNIPR/ participants: UPV, TUC, IST-ID, CERTE and BU). The aim of Task 3.4 is to simulate different future scenarios considering the impact of climate and socio-economic changes on groundwater resources at the five pilot sites. At this aim, different surrogate models were developed for each case study. The surrogate models will support the implementation of the Fuzzy WebDSS tool (WP6) aimed at assist decision makers in aquifer management. The M3.4 outlines the definition of climate and socio-economic scenarios and reports the application of surrogate models within the context of the selected scenarios.

1. Introduction

InTheMED aims to develop new easy-to-use smart models that enable the assessment of alternative scenarios with small computation time. Surrogate models are simplified models that approximate the behavior of more complex and computationally expensive models.

For Requena-Utiel (Spain), Konya (Turkey) and Tympaki (Greece), the surrogate models are based on the results of complete numerical models. Random Forest and Artificial Neural Network machine learning algorithms were used for the first two case studies, while the third one employed a spatiotemporal geostatistical model. For Grombalia (Tunisia) and Castro Verde (Portugal), surrogate models were developed using a statistical approach that relies on regression models, as numerical models were not available.

The calibrated models will be used to analyse the effects of climate change and hypothetical scenarios of socio-economic activities that may alter groundwater resources. For example, a calibrated groundwater model could be used to simulate the impacts of changes in precipitation patterns due to climate change on groundwater recharge rates. Similarly, the model could be used to simulate the impacts of changes in land use or water use practices on groundwater resources. With this purpose, different scenarios were investigated for each pilot site in order to provide valuable information for policymakers and resource managers in developing strategies to mitigate the impacts of climate and socio-economic changes on groundwater resources.

The following sections present the definition of the climate and socio-economic scenarios and the application of the surrogate models under the selected scenarios.

2. Case Studies

2.1. Requena-Utiel (Spain)

Introduction

The exploitation of the Requena-Utiel aquifer (Figure 1) over the past two decades has caused its water levels to show a progressive decrease and the aquifer storage balance to be negative, which indicates its emptying, which may worsen due to the effects of climate change. Numerical models are fundamental for determining the best management scenarios in that situation. On the one hand, their configuration, build and run require large computational time in addition to specialized knowledge. On the other, as highlighted by the stakeholders in the living lab that took place in the study area on the 4th of March 2022 (A. Godoy et al., 2023), one of the weaknesses in the groundwater management process is the lack of reliable and accessible (i.e., noncomplex) information and tools to monitor the aquifer state. In this sense, based on a complete numerical model, the UPV team has developed a smart (or surrogate) model by Random Forest (Breiman, 2001), whose primary purpose is to replace the numerical model in the prediction of groundwater levels in response to changes in recharge and/or pumping. The smart model is an innovative tool that can be used to analyse the impact of future climate scenarios and groundwater use in the groundwater levels.

Definition of Scenarios

The impact of future climate was represented by the impact in the recharge that, for this aquifer, is mainly due to precipitation. According to the climatic projections reported in Deliverable 3.3 (D’Oria et al., 2022), it was assumed that in 36 years, the recharge could present a variation of plus/minus 30% of the average of the last ten years. That means that the change in the recharge rate follows a linear function (increasing or decreasing) in time, with zero change for the first month (#1) and a maximum change (+/- 30%) for the last month (#432) modelled.

The impact of groundwater use was represented by changes in the actual pumping rate of all operating wells. Pumping wells were considered possible to fluctuate in plus/minus 25% of the average of the last ten years, and this change is applied directly to each time step. The maximum reduction of 25% was defined based on the reduction required for the total pumping

rights be less than the available resources, that is, to convert the aquifer storage balance into positive. The Júcar Water Authority, the water management body of the watershed of the study area, calculated the storage balance as part of the Hydrological Plan for the 2022-2027 term (CHJ, 2023). The maximum increase of 25% in the pumping rate was considered as an extreme and unsustainable condition.

Figure 1. Location of the Requena-Utiel aquifer

Once the intervals of variations of the recharge and pumping rates were defined, eight values were sampled to represent the recharge and pumping scenarios. These values were combined to generate 64 scenarios. Table 1 shows the values used to define the scenarios.

Table 1. Used increase and reduction scenarios for pumping and recharge rate

	% increase/reduction							
Recharge	+30%	+21%	+13%	+4.3%	-4.3%	-13%	-21%	-30%
Pumping	+25%	+18%	+10%	+3.5%	-3.5%	-10%	-18%	-25%

Application of the Surrogate Models Under Different Scenarios

The trained surrogate model was used to predict groundwater levels at 110 selected locations considering 64 scenarios for the period 2016-2052, which is discretized in 432 months. The performance of the random forest is described in detail in Deliverable 3.2 (Todaro et al., 2023). The random forest takes four features as input: the month (from October 2016 to September 2052), the year (from 2016 to 2052), the recharge factor (Table 1), and the pumping rate factor (Table 1) as defined above.

Once trained, the random forest is used to predict groundwater levels at selected locations for the different scenarios described in the previous section.

2.2. Tympaki (Greece)

Introduction

The Tympaki area is located on the southern coast of Crete, Greece, and is known for its agricultural production (Figure 2). Due to overpumping, the groundwater level has dropped more than 20 m in the last two decades causing a significant problem: seawater intrusion into the Tympaki aquifer. A full numerical hydrogeologic model using FEFLOW has been developed for the Tympaki Basin to enable reliable modelling and sustainable use of groundwater resources. However, an alternative is a surrogate model based on the proposed hydrogeologic model that can simulate groundwater level fluctuations with minimal computational effort and allow evaluation of various climatic and socioeconomic scenarios.

Figure 2. Tympaki study area land use

A surrogate model for the groundwater resources within the area would require spatiotemporal data on relevant variables such as temperature, precipitation, soil properties, crop yields, and other environmental factors that affect groundwater dynamics. Such a model may be a viable alternative to numerical models which are often very computationally and time-consuming. A surrogate model can be built based on available data using statistical and machine-learning techniques to accurately capture the spatiotemporal patterns in the data. Space-time regression kriging (STRK) models are popular for building surrogate models for groundwater systems. STRK models are able to capture complex spatiotemporal patterns in the data, account for uncertainties and provide probabilistic estimates of the important variables.

A STRK model of groundwater levels for the Tympaki aquifer was developed using groundwater level data recorded at 11 wells for the period 2004-2020 together with some auxiliary variables: the elevation at each well location from a Digital Elevation Model; the mean annual rainfall trend for the period 2004-2020 through an exponentially-weighted-moving-average (EWMA) filter (Varouchakis and Hristopulos 2019); the spatial average of groundwater level in the area from the 53 monitoring wells of the reference year 2019-2020; the spatial average of the agreed pumping rates at the pumping wells operating in the area. Predictions were made in the monitoring locations and in a 50x50 grid of the case study area based on different future climate change, pumping and groundwater level scenarios.

Definition of Scenarios

As climate change continues to alter rainfall patterns and increase the frequency and severity of droughts and floods, sustainable water resources management becomes increasingly important. This includes implementing practices and policies that prioritize the long-term availability of water resources while meeting the needs of water users. The water resources directorate of Crete has suggested the following scenarios in terms of the current conditions regarding overall groundwater level increase and pumping reduction due to the operation of water reservoir in the case study area:

- 1st scenario: 50% pumping reduction, 20% average groundwater level increase (optimistic scenario)
- 2nd scenario 80% pumping reduction, 50% average groundwater level increase (promising scenario)

The aforementioned scenarios were implemented through the regression model components of the spatially averaged groundwater level over all the monitoring wells and the spatially averaged pumping over all the pumping wells.

For rainfall variability projections the mean exponentially-weighted-moving-average (EWMA) filter impact (Varouchakis and Hristopulos 2019) of six climate models (Table 2) for two emission pathways (RCP4.5 and RCP8.5) was considered. The climate scenarios were downscaled for the site by the UNIPR team (D'Oria et al. 2022).

Table 2. Considered climate change models for RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5

'CNRM_CERFACS_CNRM_CM5_CCLM4_8_17'
'DMI_HIRHAM5_NorESM1-M'
'ICHEC_EC_EARTH_HIRHAM5'
'IPSL-INERIS_WRF381P_IPSL-CM5A-MR'
'KNMI_CNRM-CM5'
'MPI_M_MPI_ESM_LR_RCA4'

The surrogate model takes into account the climate projections for the period 2021-2039 for the study area (D'Oria et al. 2022) and the hydrological year characteristics (wet above 500 mm/dry below 500 mm; Akrouf et al. 2021). The surrogate model can easily examine the

possible scenarios described above and defined by the water resources directorate of the region of Crete.

The surrogate model can also be used for comparison and sensitivity analysis to understand the importance of groundwater level and pumping fluctuation scenarios on groundwater dynamics. In order to assess any scenarios for the groundwater level variations, a spatial groundwater level (GWL) variation coefficient, ranging from 0 to 2, and a spatial pumping rate coefficient, ranging from -1 to 1, can be considered. For the former, 1 denotes no change from the current spatial average groundwater level conditions, while 0 denotes 100% decrement and 2 denotes a 100% increment. On the other hand, for the pumping coefficient, 0 corresponds to the current spatial average pumping conditions, while -1 corresponds to 100% reduction (stop pumping) and 1 to 100% increase of pumping rates.

Application of the Surrogate Models Under Different Scenarios

The training, validation and evaluation of the STRK model at the scale of a hydrologic year are described in detail in Deliverable 3.2 (Todaro et al., 2023). The surrogate model was then implemented in a graphical user interface GUI (Figure 3) to allow the user to evaluate and compare different scenarios. Once the STRK model has been trained, predictions can be made for groundwater levels at the monitoring wells and at unobserved locations in a future hydrologic year. Groundwater level predictions were made explicitly at the 53 monitoring points (Figure 3) where the STRK model was validated for the hydrologic year 2019-2020. It is assumed that these monitoring wells (sites) will continue to operate in the area, allowing for a continued validation and improvement of model predictions.

Overall, the creation of a reliable surrogate model for the geostatistical space-time study of groundwater levels in the Tympaki area would involve dynamic analysis of the behaviour of the aquifer under different groundwater level and pumping scenarios.

Figure 3. Graphical User Interface implementing the STRK model at the study area

2.3. Konya (Turkey)

Introduction

The Konya basin is an important agricultural region in Turkey, with over 50% of its plain surface dedicated to agricultural activities (Figure 4). However, the lack of rivers and streams within the Konya basin has led to heavy reliance on groundwater resources to meet the agricultural demands, particularly during the dry periods. As a consequence, the groundwater reserves in the basin are under considerable pressure. In recent years, there has been a gradual shift from traditional wheat farming to more profitable crops such as sugar beets and maize, which require more water (Yilmaz et al., 2021). Furthermore, projected climate change is expected to further exacerbate the situation and, together with overexploitation, can jeopardize its sustainability.

With the aim of promoting sustainable use of groundwater resources, a full numerical hydrogeological model for the Konya basin was developed by the BU Team. Based on the developed hydrogeological model, the ultimate objective is to implement a surrogate model that replaces the full model and simulate groundwater flow within the Konya closed basin with a low computational burden allowing the evaluation of different climate and socio-economic scenarios.

In particular, an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) was implemented, which serves as a valuable tool to support decision-making processes and help promote the sustainable use of the basin's groundwater resources. The purpose of the smart model is intended to provide predictions of future groundwater levels under various climate change and irrigation/crop scenarios.

Figure 4. Turkey: study area, satellite land use map of Konya Closed Basin for year of 2018

Definition of Scenarios

The surrogate model is used to analyse the possible effects of climate change and agricultural policies on groundwater considering as driven input different pattern of future precipitation and water demand scenarios.

The investigated prediction period spans from 2020 to 2039. Three different future precipitation scenarios were considered, based on the information of the historical precipitation in the period (2000-2019). The first precipitation scenario considers a - 20% of the historical precipitation in the 2020-2039 period (Prec. -20%), the second precipitation scenario considers the same historical precipitation pattern for the prediction period and the last scenario considers + 20% of the historical precipitation in the 2020-2039 period (Prec. +20%).

For each precipitation scenario the crop water demand was considered in the range $\pm 20\%$ of the historical water demand.

Application of the Surrogate Models Under Different Scenarios

The ANN surrogate model is used to predict groundwater levels at 30 monitoring points within the Konya closed basin considering various climate and agricultural scenarios for the period 2020-2039, which is discretized in 240 months.

The training, validation and testing of the ANN are described in detail in Deliverable 3.2 (Todaro et al., 2023). The ANN takes three features as input: the precipitation coefficient, the crop coefficient and the lead time. The precipitation and crop coefficients were applied to historical rainfall and water demand data, respectively. The lead time is the number of months from January 2020 for which the output is required; it spans from 1 to 240. The ANN gives as output the piezometric heads at the 30 monitoring points at the selected lead time.

Once fully trained, the network will be used to predict groundwater levels for the different scenarios described in the previous section.

2.4. Grombalia (Tunisia)

Introduction

Grombalia groundwater faces a higher risk of depletion. One of the main factors contributing to the depletion of groundwater in Grombalia is the overextraction of water from the aquifers. The increasing demand for water, especially for agriculture, has led to a significant increase in the number of wells and pumping stations in the region. In addition to overextraction, climate change is exacerbating the problem in Grombalia (Todaro et al., 2022). The region is already characterized by a semi-arid climate with low rainfall, and climate change is projected to lead to further declines in groundwater levels.

The surrogate model developed for the Grombalia aquifer aims to provide a useful tool for evaluating the impact of future climate scenarios on groundwater resources. Since a complete numerical model is not available for the study area, a data-driven surrogate model has been developed based on historical groundwater levels, precipitation, and temperature data. The proposed method employs easy and fast statistical techniques to assess the possible effects of climate change on the quantitative status of groundwater, combining historical relationships between meteorological and groundwater data with future climate scenarios. Assuming that hydrological processes will not change over time, the surrogate model can make predictions

about how the aquifer will respond to changes in climate variables. Figure 5 shows the investigated area and the location of the meteorological stations and monitoring wells. Overall, the surrogate model provides a quick and efficient way to assess the potential impact of climate change on the Grombalia aquifer without the need for a complete numerical model.

Figure 5. Tunisia: study area and location of the temperature and rain stations and monitoring wells

Definition of Scenarios

For this pilot site, the impact of climate change on groundwater resources is analysed under two climate scenarios: the Representative Concentration Pathways RCP4.5 and the RCP8.5. The RCP4.5 scenario assumes that greenhouse gas emissions will peak around 2040 and then decline, reaching a radiative forcing of 4.5 W/m² by 2100. This scenario assumes moderate emissions reductions and greater use of low-carbon energy sources. In contrast, the RCP8.5 scenario assumes that greenhouse gas emissions will continue to rise throughout the century, resulting in a radiative forcing of 8.5 W/m² by 2100. This scenario assumes a business-as-usual approach to emissions with little to no mitigation efforts. The evaluation of the impact of the

anthropogenic actions cannot be considered as the surrogate model developed for Grombalia (Tunisia) is driven by precipitation and temperature variations only.

Application of the Surrogate Models Under Different Scenarios

For the Grombalia pilot site, the surrogate model is a linear regression between groundwater levels (GWLs) and standard precipitation-evapotranspiration indices (SPEIs), which means that there is a linear relationship between these two variables (Secci et al., 2021). This relationship was established based on a correlation analysis of the available historical data of GWLs and precipitation and temperature, which are used to compute the historical SPEIs. The correlation analysis and the development of the surrogate model are described in detail in Deliverable 3.2 (Todaro et al., 2023). The surrogate model has been developed based on late winter and early spring months data and considering the wells that present at least a Pearson correlation coefficient greater than 0.7, resulting in eight correlated wells. For each well, the SPEI accumulation periods in months, the Pearson correlation coefficient between GWLs and SPEIs and the regression coefficients are reported in Table 3.

Table 3. Tunisia: name and codes of the monitoring wells, the SPEI accumulation periods in months, the Pearson correlation coefficient between GWLs and SPEIs and the regression coefficients

Well code	Well name	SPEI time window (month)	r (-)	Regression line	
				Intercept (m a.s.l.)	Slope (m a.s.l.)
W1	12440	36	0.83	34.08	1.03
W3	2183	24	0.82	19.29	1.04
W4	2171	18	0.83	22.60	0.74
W6	2543	12	0.74	9.42	0.74
W8	2008	24	0.91	62.26	1.31
W17	8844	24	0.71	41.73	0.96
W18	2379	36	0.74	1.79	0.36
W20	12405	12	0.89	17.60	1.75

Once established the surrogate model, which is a linear relationship for each individual well, will be used to evaluate the future groundwater levels based on future SPEI values. The future SPEIs were estimated using precipitation and temperature data provided by an ensemble of regional climate models (RCMs) under the climate scenarios RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 (Todaro et al., 2022). The climate model data used in this work are described in Deliverable 3.3 (D’Oria et al., 2022).

2.5. Castro Verde (Portugal)

Introduction

The Castro Verde case study belongs to the Portuguese South Zone of the Guadiana Basin groundwater system. The Guadiana Basin is heavily dependent on groundwater for agriculture, industry, and drinking water. The increasing water demand has led to a significant increase in the number of wells and pumping stations in the region. Climate change is also a significant factor affecting groundwater depletion in the Guadiana Basin (Todaro et al., 2022). The region is experiencing more frequent and severe droughts, reducing the amount of rainfall and surface water available for recharge. Higher temperatures also increase the demand for water for irrigation and other uses, exacerbating the problem of overexploitation.

The surrogate model developed for the Guadiana aquifer aims to provide a useful tool for evaluating the impact of future climate scenarios on groundwater resources. Since a complete numerical model is not available for the study area, a data-driven surrogate model has been developed based on historical groundwater levels, precipitation, and temperature data. The proposed method employs easy and fast statistical techniques to assess the possible effects of climate change on the quantitative status of groundwater, combining historical relationships between meteorological and groundwater data with future climate scenarios. Assuming that hydrological processes will not change over time, the surrogate model can make predictions about how the aquifer will respond to changes in climate variables. Figure 6 shows the investigated area and the location of the meteorological stations and monitoring wells.

Overall, the surrogate model provides a quick and efficient way to assess the potential impact of climate change on the Guadiana aquifer without the need for a complete numerical model.

Figure 6. Portugal: study area and location of the temperature and rain stations and monitoring wells

Definition of Scenarios

For this pilot site, the impact of climate change on groundwater resources is analysed under two climate scenarios: the Representative Concentration Pathways RCP4.5 and the RCP8.5. The RCP4.5 scenario assumes that greenhouse gas emissions will peak around 2040 and then decline, reaching a radiative forcing of 4.5 W/m² by 2100. This scenario assumes moderate emissions reductions and greater use of low-carbon energy sources. In contrast, the RCP8.5 scenario assumes that greenhouse gas emissions will continue to rise throughout the century, resulting in a radiative forcing of 8.5 W/m² by 2100. This scenario assumes a business-as-usual approach to emissions with little to no mitigation efforts. The evaluation of the impact of the anthropogenic actions cannot be considered as the surrogate model developed for Guadiana aquifer system is driven by precipitation and temperature variations only.

Application of the Surrogate Models Under Different Scenarios

For the Castro Verde pilot site, the surrogate model is a linear regression between groundwater levels (GWLs) and standard precipitation-evapotranspiration indices (SPEIs), which means that

there is a linear relationship between these two variables (Secci et al., 2021). This relationship was established based on a correlation analysis of the available historical data of GWLs and precipitation and temperature, which are used to compute the historical SPEIs. The correlation analysis and the development of the surrogate model are described in detail in Deliverable 3.2 (Todaro et al., 2023). The surrogate model has been developed based on late winter and early spring months data and considering the wells that present at least a Pearson correlation coefficient greater than 0.7, resulting in six correlated wells. For each well, the SPEI accumulation periods in months, the Pearson correlation coefficient between GWLs and SPEIs and the linear regression coefficients are reported in Table 4.

Table 4. Portugal: name and codes of the monitoring wells, the SPEI accumulation periods in months, the Pearson correlation coefficient between GWLs and SPEIs and the linear regression coefficients

Well name	SPEI time window (month)	r (-)	Regression line	
			Intercept (m a.s.l.)	Slope (m a.s.l.)
581/41	3	0.72	382.58	0.46
400/7	24	0.92	189.32	1.79
512/32	18	0.73	190.71	1.44
513/34	24	0.87	199.32	2.16
524/49	12	0.76	249.62	4.15
600/24	36	0.91	3.63	1.11

Once established the surrogate model, which is a linear relationship for each individual well, will be used to evaluate the future groundwater levels based on future SPEI values. The future SPEIs were estimated using precipitation and temperature data provided by an ensemble of regional climate models (RCMs) under the climate scenarios RCP 4.5 and RCP 8.5 (Todaro et al., 2022). The climate model data used in this work are described in Deliverable 3.3 (D’Oria et al., 2022).

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